

A WEBERIAN PERSPECTIVE TO STRATIFICATION IN THE WORKPLACE

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ABSTRACT

Inequality exists in various forms in different societies, ranging from unequal distribution allocation of goods and services to differentials in reward allocations and classification of people and groups into hierarchical layers based on prestige and wealth.

These classifications based on socio-economic standing are inherent in workplace settings like they are in the society at large. They have been explained from various schools of thought by various sociologists over the years of which a common one is the Weberian idea which posits that three interdependent factors namely status, prestige and power shape the stratification hierarchy.

The paper examines the realities of the class relations in work organizations over the years in relation to the Weberian school of thought for areas of convergence.

1.0 CONCEPT OF STRATIFICATION

Inequality exists in all complex societies in various forms. A good example is how prized goods are allocated unequally in the society, another is the classification of definite groups one above the other in terms of aspects such as prestige and wealth. Social stratification system bears on the social institutions that give rise to observed inequalities of this nature.

Social stratification is the term sociologists apply to the ranking or grading of individuals and groups into hierarchical layers, representing the structured inequality in allocation of rewards, privileges and resources. This infers that some individuals are more privileged than others just by virtue of their roles or group membership. The key components of stratification systems are:

- i) The processes defining what goods are desirable and valuable
- ii) The rules guiding the allocation and distribution of these goods across various positions of labour (e.g. farmer, housewife, nurse, doctor)
- iii) The mobility mechanisms that links individuals to positions thereby generating control over valued resources

Groups are therefore stratified on basis of in socio-economic standing, awareness of common interests and common identity. Members of a distinct class are graced with similar quota and types of resources.

1.2 Theoretical Perspectives

The common theoretical perspectives from which sociologists explain social stratification are the Functionalist, Marxian, and Weberian perspectives.

The functionalist perspective: Functionalists believe that every society requires people who can be placed and motivated for certain tasks and that these tasks have social positions and duties attached to them. Functionalists believe individuals are assigned specific positions based on their eligibility and criteria and that positions not being the same means some require special training and are more functionally important than others. For example, a policeman's job being more important than that of a salesgirl at a supermarket will attract a better reward. The role of a

supermarket salesgirl does not require the same skill and training level as that of a policeman and without incentives such as higher pay and benefit why would a policeman take risks associated with policing while they could just work as a supermarket salesperson as well.

Based on functional logic, society has different rewards and these rewards are distributed based on one's social position. Therefore, social order is created which constitute of rewards and distribution pattern laying the foundation for the stratification system in the society.

Marxist perspective: Unlike functionalists, Marxists regard stratification as divisive rather than integrative. Marxists believe the existence of social strata with social interests promotes social inequality and exploitation in a system. Marxists are also known as critical sociologists.

The Marxist approach highlight conflict as a distinguishing feature of a stratified society. The conflict being between the two broad social classes with opposite status over the distribution of scarce resources and economic value. The two recognized classes are the Bourgeoisies or Capitalists or Owners of the means of production and the Proletariats or Working class. The scarcity aspect is important here because it yields power to the owners (capitalists or haves) while non-owners (working class or have nots) are deprived.

Marxists believe the great income inequality between the capitalists and the working-class is a result of the corporate elites' ability and capacity to accord hefty salaries and bonuses to themselves. According to Karl Marx, the feeling of deprivation in the non-owners will eventually lead to a class consciousness which will get accumulated and become instrumental in a fight for social change which could lead to common ownership/communism.

Marxists also believe the political and legal system of societies is designed to support the domination of the ruling class over the subject class. They believe the ruling class is controlled directly or indirectly by the capitalists.

Weberian perspective: Max Weber contended the Marxian school of thought on social stratification with the claim that stratification was based on more than simply ownership of capital, arguing that people who manage corporations without owning them still benefit from the increased production and inequality of income. He also used the example of how members of the

aristocracy lacked economic wealth yet had a strong political power to explain how three independent factors form his theory of stratification hierarchy.

The three interdependent factors that shape stratification hierarchy according to him are class, status, and power. Class refers to a person's economic standing or level of wealth in the society while status refers to one's prestige, reputation and fame in the society; and power is possession of control, authority, or influence over others of others. These factors are intertwined in the sense that wealth or economic standing or ownership of property can bring about prestige especially because people in the society hold the rich in high regard. On the other hand, prestige from other sources such as intellectual prowess, specialist skills can also lead to wealth or ownership of property if people are willing to pay for access to the prestige.

However, while these factors wealth, status, and power are intertwined, it is possible to have a high status without enormous wealth or to have wealth without power.

2.0 WEBERIAN PERSPECTIVE TO SOCIAL STRATIFICATION IN THE WORKPLACE

The key features peculiar of the Weberian idea of stratification can be analyzed from the workplace relations perspective in from the perspective that each of the key factors namely wealth, status and power identified as determinants of social standing can be associated with the various distinct actors involved in workplace relations.

Analyzing from the macro level, the three actors in workplace relations, being the employers/owner of means of productions/organizations' management/employer associations, the workers/workers' representative/labour unions and the State/Government possess varying amounts of the Weberian factors namely class/wealth, prestige/status and power. The corporate elites/ organizations' management/employer associations are known to hold a high level of wealth being the owners, and/or managers of the production processes, the State being the chief regulator and principal actor in the workplace relations holds a lot of political power while the workers that exchange their labour for wages have the ability to earn themselves prestige, admiration and fame in the society (otherwise known as 'status' as propounded by Weber) for being exceptionally good at what they do and by developing specialized skills, intellectual prowess and/or acquisition of high level education.

Acquisition of this specialized skills, training, education, and professional or intellectual prowess can bring about wealth for members of the working class, especially if their fields are those in high demand. It could also help them move up the ladder from workers, supervisors or foremen to business managers, which would make them members of the corporate elites which comes with much more higher levels of income. The corporate elites and owners of the means of production by virtue of the high level of wealth they possess can also earn admiration and prestige in the society, especially with the value system in most societies of the world today being built around wealth and riches.

The ability of both the working class and the corporate elites to win peoples admiration in the society leading to a high level of prestige makes it not impossible for member of any of the two distinct groups to gain enough popularity to contest for and emerge as a political office holder.

This can be referred to as seeking positions of power using political means. Emergence as a political office holder would translate to membership of the ruling class (which was previously correlated with the State/Government and its officials in the paper). Thus, the concepts of status, prestige, and power even in the workplace are intertwined and are not entirely mutually exclusive.

However, the wealth of the corporate elites and owners of production processes is not enough to give them the level or kind of power the political elites and the state possess in legitimately regulating conducts and the maintenance of order in the society. This is just as workers representative/labour unions with the mass power in their hands as much as workplace relations is concerned due to their large membership still cannot stand shoulder to shoulder with the organizations' management/employer associations as regards wealth, riches, and economic standing. This explains Max Weber's stance that it is possible to have a high status without enormous wealth or to have wealth without power.

Explaining from the organizational level, independent of the State, the Weberian stratum model can be broken down to three categories in the workplace: the wealthy and powerful class that own and/or control the means of production (with property and tagged upper class); a class of skilled, salaried workers made up of professionals, specialists, and the petty bourgeoisies (mainly property-less intellectuals and tagged middle class); and a class mainly consisting of semi-skilled and unskilled workers who rely on hourly wages for livelihood such as clerks, labourers etc. (tagged lower class).

Despite the clear distinctions between these three classes, status honour ascribed to them may not necessarily be linked with the class situation. Power again becomes a crucial element, as there can be socially and economically derived power. Power according to Weber is the ability to influence behaviour of others or the course of events. Socially derived power arises from social and personal ethos and it is not impossible to find people that wield a considerable level of such powers among the property-less groups. Economically derived honour on the other hand stems from ownership of property and wealth and is usually ascribed to the owners and controllers of production processes.

While economic power can help attain social, it still cannot be recognized as the basis for social honour. Rather, social honour can be the basis of political or economic power. This simply means belonging to the wealthy workplace group with the highest forms of monetary rewards does not guarantee acceptance, widespread respect, or admiration as honour means different things to different people.

Social honour which refers to acceptance, widespread respect, or admiration by the general workplace populace, can be a basis of economic or political power. Political power in the sense that such acceptance can be used to attain positions of power that require the members of the organization's vote or acceptance such as trade union leadership or heads of workplace committees, thus earning political power. There have been cases of people performing well in such political offices by demonstrating their ability to lead and coordinate functions getting to top management positions, or simply by building on their competencies by acquiring higher-level education to move up the hierarchical ladder to become a member of the higher-level classes. This explains the stance of the concepts of status, prestige, and power being intertwined even in workplace settings. It is worthy to note acquisition of education and specialist skills is key to upward mobility in this context.

Conclusion

The social class or stratification systems in work organizations cannot be classified solely based on relationship to the means of productions because there are people that do not own the means of production but by their positions control the systems of production and wield similar levels of socio-economic power to the owners of the means of production.

Thus, the Weberian school of thought posits that three interdependent factors which are class, prestige, and power shape social stratification hierarchy and that possession of a high level of any of these factors can bring about acquisition of any of the others, while it is also very possible to possess a high level of one of the factors without being able to boast of another. Above all, education and specialized skill is a major determinant of class position rather than relationship to the means of production as against the principles of the Marxists. This is because the acquisition of education and specialized skill is the key criteria responsible for movement up the social class hierarchy, especially as far as the workplace is concerned.

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